
BEYOND THE CALL: MOTIVATION AND PRACTICE OF NORTHERN IRELAND'S GRASSROOTS PEACEBUILDERS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20054040>

A B S T R A C T	KEY WORDS
Northern Ireland's peace process operates across multiple strategic levels, yet much scholarly attention has focused on top- and middle-tier peacebuilding initiatives, leaving grassroots efforts relatively underexplored. This study examines the role of grassroots peace practitioners, analyzing how personal motivation and professional practice intersect within community-level peacebuilding. Drawing on Lederach's (1997) peacebuilding pyramid as a conceptual framework, the research highlights the significance of local actors in sustaining peace and addressing the legacies of conflict. By systematically reflecting on past methodologies and practices, this study aims to identify effective strategies that respond to the evolving needs of communities navigating post-conflict challenges. Understanding the motivations, experiences, and approaches of grassroots practitioners not only contributes to academic discourse but also informs practical frameworks for ongoing engagement in divided societies. This research underscores the importance of integrating community perspectives into broader peacebuilding strategies, ensuring that lessons from grassroots practice enhance both policy and practice in Northern Ireland and comparable post-conflict contexts.	Grassroots peacebuilding; Northern Ireland; conflict legacy; community engagement; peace practice

Introduction

Northern Ireland's peace process has multiple strategic tracks. While much has been written analyzing Northern Ireland's peacebuilding activity at the top and middle-range levels, to use Lederach's (1997) peacebuilding pyramid designations, generally activity at Northern Ireland's grassroots level deserves more systematic study. The grassroots layer has been acknowledged by academics in the field of peace and conflict, yet as Kelly and Braniff (2016) recommend, "it remains crucial that a more effective understanding of what has worked to date is developed, so that the methodologies used to guide continued engagement are based on considered reflection of past practice as well as being driven by the continually changing demands of a society which continues to grapple with the legacy of its violent past" (p.16).

Members of the Northern Ireland peace practitioner community have sustained their careers-long dedication to constructive local engagement across the deep historical divide throughout the decades of the Troubles, the post-

agreement era, and up to the present. An exploration of their development as individual practitioners and as a community of practice will contribute to our understanding of grassroots level peacebuilding in a climate of conflict and violence followed by a post agreement's uncertain mix of hope and tension.

Before presenting the results of our qualitative study, our literature review will locate the work of Northern Ireland's local peace practitioners within existing academic analyses of local peacebuilding processes. We will identify our grounding concepts, which together provide an explanation for the development and impact of Northern Ireland's peace practitioner community. Central to their practice of grassroots intercommunity peacebuilding, the practitioners in our study formed a stable community of practice (CoP) (Wenger et al., 2002) built upon an emergent practical wisdom (Stanton, 2021) and a steadfast commitment to a common good (Parks Daloz et al., 1996).

Developing Professionalized Form and Focus

The evolution and organization of grassroots peace practitioners in Northern Ireland have occurred over the last 55+ years of The Troubles and the post Belfast (Good Friday) Agreement era. Their beginnings can be tracked to the late 1960s when neighbors helped neighbors burned out of their homes during sporadic acts of violence. Such spontaneous, across-the-historical-divide acts of courage were supported by voluntary sector organizations which provided emergency assistance and refuge for fleeing families, for example Quakers (LeMare & McCartney, 2009) and the Corrymeela Community (Davey, 1993). Neighborhood residents initiated cross community contacts, such as the grassroots group that became Protestant and Catholic Encounter (PACE) began in 1969 (Stanton, 2021). Amid increasing violence in 1971 when the British government interned suspected paramilitary members, Quakers expanded their aid for prisoners' families. After Bloody Sunday in January 1972 ignited what became known as The Troubles, neighborhood peace endeavors multiplied as well. Peace People became one of the best known when its leaders received the Nobel Peace Prize in 1976.

From such beginnings peacebuilding leadership evolved and expanded rooted in the courage and creativity of grassroots people. Stanton (2021) provides an informative survey of grassroots and civil society peacebuilding from 1965 to 2015. Her six phases of The Troubles framework effectively documents the extensive, diverse, and multifaceted initiatives produced by Northern Ireland's grassroots peacebuilders. Their efforts included neighborhood cross-community phone networks to forestall rumor-induced violence and women information-sharing via putting-on-the-kettle conversations. Larger-scale endeavors produced extensive, multiple year projects and programs marking the start of more formal/structured professional partnerships. For example, in 1981, with their own funds, several members of All Children Together (ACT) started Lagan College, the first integrated secondary school, and in 1990, the first professionalized local mediation NGO, the Mediation Network for Northern Ireland, was established (Stanton, 2021). As Corrymeela's founder Ray Davey (1993, p. 136) observed:

For the first time in our history there are not only occasional individuals who crusade for peace, but over the last ten to twenty years more and more new organizations and pressure groups have come into existence. These are made up of multitudes of people who long for peace and are determined to work for it. This is a new phenomenon, and it will not go away.

By the late 1980s Northern Ireland's peacebuilding advocates were making the case for a statutory body to provide a focus, an institutional imprimatur. The Community Relations Council (CRC) was formed in 1990 "in order to support and promote community relations work at all levels within the community" (Frazer & Fitzduff,

1994, p. 3). This statutory institutionalization of support for inter and intracommunity peace work had a precedent. In 1969 an earlier effort had taken the form of a Ministry for Community Relations and a Community Relations Commission. These earlier statutory bodies disbanded with the fall of Northern Ireland's first power sharing government in 1974. The 1990 launch of the CRC happened at a time when grassroots peacebuilding had developed to the point that 37 reconciliation groups completed and returned the consultation questionnaire (Frazer & Fitzduff, 1994).

From its start the CRC advocated for and funded peacebuilding. The CRC's form, its operational activities, included publishing training books and other information useful for doing the work of local peacebuilding. Prior to becoming the CRC's first Director, Mari

Fitzduff published a 1988 handbook for group work on community relations and in 1989 *A Typology of Community Relations Work*. Both books became tools-of-the-trade and were reprinted several times by the CRC. In both its form and focus the CRC effectively channeled major new funding, particularly from the European Union, into an increasing number of local peace projects. Thus the succession of events leading up to the 1998 Belfast (Good Friday) Agreement occurred in the context of increased local peacebuilding. While the Stormont government's functioning became intermittent, grassroots peace practitioners expanded the nature and number of community sector projects, thus adding to the layers of local people with proven program relevant expertise and personal contacts developed over decades.

The term "professionalism" was applied to the community sector's capabilities by an extensive research review carried out by INCORE, the University of Ulster's peace center. The 2010 study included in-depth interviewing of key individuals in the political and policy making, the civic and business, and the community and voluntary sectors. According to the final report, "Respondents noted positively the significant capacity and professionalism that exists within the (community/voluntary) sector, particularly among those engaged in work with impacts directly on good relations objectives" (Kelly, 2012, p. 105).

The issue of the political/statutory sector and the community sector having underlying differences is directly stated in a publication by a well-known community sector practitioner: I believe that the *real* untold story of the Troubles – concerns the constant efforts made by ordinary people to initiate dialogue, efforts repeatedly thwarted not only by forces within their own communities but by a political establishment which resented any intrusion upon its well-entrenched interests (Hall, 2020, p. 3).

One of the vital skills developed by people in the grassroots practitioner community was balancing and synthesizing the variety of potentially incompatible interests and perspectives. Given these practitioners' importance to Northern Ireland's peacefully slogging through its deeply divisive long-term issues, our first research objective is to consider the reason(s) for the practitioners' persistence in their work. Available information about Northern Ireland's community of grassroots practitioners indicates how many have spent their whole careers in small scale, laterally structured, local organizations, working on a succession of competitively funded projects, without the benefit of upward mobility, the status that comes with it, and the security of a retirement fund. Yet Northern Ireland's practitioners – demonstrably intelligent, hard-working, able, experienced, and creative people have continued their work through trying times. These have included the Stormont government's episodic suspensions as well as incidents of violence sparked by intermittent times of tension, for example some commemoration parades, Belfast's flag controversy, and, more recently, Brexit. Understanding their enduring motivation could prove helpful in identifying and recruiting the next generation of practitioners needed to continue Northern

Ireland's commitment to peace as well as framing incentives to encourage new community sector organizations. Our study's second research objective will address how Northern Ireland's grassroots practitioners create, refine, and renew their practice, particularly as indicative of a process of professionalization. We define practice as the shared body of tacit and explicit knowledge developed and maintained to address community peace building. Reiman and Ropers (2005) note that "CSOs (civil society organizations) have to understand themselves as learning organizations making organizational capacity building and team development one of its priorities" (p. 38). And as Kelly and Braniff (2016) advocated, best practices from the past should inform current practice. Over the decades of grassroots community projects, several have produced training materials of their own. For example, O'Hagan's (2008) *Training Manual: Towards Understanding and Healing* and another publication, Sheridan and Hamber's (2011) *The Evaluation of Storytelling as a Peace-building Methodology*, provide examples of practitioners' reflecting on their practice. The subject of how grassroots peace practitioners' systematically attend to their practice as an ongoing process remains an important subject for research.

Guiding Research Concepts

Drawing primarily from social science theory and research, our objective is to expand our understanding of grassroots peacebuilding and shared leadership. We will apply Parks Daloz et al.'s (1996) dimensions of individual commitment, organizational theories from community of practice (CoPs) literature, and Stanton's (2021) concept of practical wisdom to our qualitative study of grassroots peace practitioners in Northern Ireland.

Commitment to a Common Good

Parks Daloz et al. (1996) examine the development of community and commitment among 100 individuals who sustained life-long commitments to work on behalf of "a common good, even in the face of global complexity, diversity, and ambiguity" (p. 5). The researchers identified how these committed people think about themselves and the world, and what led them to live and work the way they do.

According to Parks Daloz et al. (1996), the common good does not refer to a shared utopian vision of society. While acknowledging that the definition of a common good is always open to interpretation, they argue that: viable views of the common good would include such core elements as a global scope, a recognition of diversity, a vision of society as composed of individuals whose own well-being is inextricably bound up with the good of the whole (p. 16).

Once committed to the common good, "people who live committed lives know they *can't not* engage with life" (p. 203).

The researchers identified a three-phase developmental process to describe how their subjects came to their committed lives: connecting in community and with "the other;" constructing meaning and commitment, accepting contradictions; and collaborating in healing work and understanding the reality of ambivalence and paradox. Inspired by their analytical lens, we examined why Northern Ireland grassroots peace practitioners are committed to a common good, and how this commitment became central to their peacebuilding practice. We learned the definition of the common good as understood by this group of peace practitioners, and how they individually identify their commitment.

A Community of Practice

As defined by Wenger et al. (2002, p. 4), communities of practice (CoPs) are "[a group] of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis." In comparison with other forms of working groups or collaborations, CoPs focus on the creation, storage, and utilization of knowledge as it relates to their primary practice (Noar et al.,

2023). CoPs have been described as an effective form of knowledge management among practitioners (Noar et al., 2023). The practical effectiveness of CoPs was first documented in business professions, but has since been confirmed in higher education, medical and health professions (Gerritsen et al., 2021; Li et al., 2009).

Wenger (2011) identified three essential CoP characteristics: (1) Domain establishes a common ground (a level of minimal competence and commitment that differentiates members from non-members) and boundaries (that enable members to determine what is worth sharing within the group). (2) Community refers to the social structure that facilitates learning through interactions and relationships with others. (3) Finally, practice is the specific knowledge that the community shares, develops, and maintains. This may include “routines, words, tools, ways of doing things, stories, gestures, symbols, genres, actions or concepts that the community has adapted in the course of its existence” (Wenger, 1998, p. 83). A CoP can be formally or informally organized, found in person or online, and exist for various durations of time (Wells et al., 2022), but their attention to practice development and maintenance remains the priority.

In their evaluation of published research on CoPs in business and health professions, Li et al. (2009) found four similarities among the groups: (1) Social interaction involves the interaction of individuals in formal or informal settings; (2) Knowledge-sharing is the process of sharing information that is relevant to the participants; (3) Knowledge-creation refers to the process of developing new ways to perform duties or to solve a problem; and (4) Identity-building is the process of acquiring a professional identity or an identity of being an expert in the field. Research continues to affirm how mutual engagement and finding ways to think and problem-solve together are essential for successful CoPs (Pyrko et al., 2017).

“Thinking together about real-life problems that people genuinely care about gives life to CoPs” (Pyrko et al., 2017, p. 403).

The central element of our research is the notion that the Northern Ireland peace practitioner community are actively engaged in a practice which defines them individually and as a community. We seek to understand how the success of the Northern Ireland peace practitioner community relies on their ability to collectively develop and maintain their practice.

Practical Wisdom

Stanton (2021) directly focused on civil society peacebuilding in Northern Ireland. Based on her experience as a practitioner, and investigations with 40 others covering 50 years, Stanton documents the emergence of what she defines as professionalized local peacebuilders. Her explanation of work within and between grassroots communities begins in the 1960s, “selected as a beginning point because social change momentum during this time saw both formal and informal efforts made by grassroots and civil society to surface structural injustices and to promote greater social and communal reconciliation and integration” (p. 7).

Stanton (2021) explains her central concept, the Aristotelian virtue of phronesis or practical wisdom as “a form of context-dependent knowledge used for practical action” (p. 11). She fleshes out this comprehensive core concept as embodying “the type of knowledge that those working within the grassroots level and within civil society have gained as a result of their experiences situated in the context of complexity, uncertainty, and instability endemic to protracted violent conflicts” (p. 11).

Stanton (2021) states that practitioners holding practical knowledge should be viewed as “knowledge creators” (p. 11). The knowledge and judgement derived from experience produce their “understanding of behavior patterns in context.” Therefore “they possess a primary source of knowledge creation, a potential tool of analysis” (p. 13).

According to Stanton (2021), practical wisdom is a form of knowledge that is context dependent and has five dimensions: (1) Experience; (2) The use of multiple forms of knowing which integrate subjective and objective experiences; (3) Organically developed through experimentation; (4) The use of patterns formed through interconnected relationships; and (5) Judgments about what to do drawn from accumulated patterns of experiences derived from trial and error or exemplars (pp. 58-59). Stanton goes on to describe the importance of engendering trust both personally and when engaging in peacebuilding.

Stanton (2021) concludes that “practitioners have been under-utilised as peacebuilding knowledge producers” (p. 38) and “further research could, however, strengthen recognition for the value of phronetic epistemologies of practice” (p. 206). In our research we will explore the process of peacebuilding knowledge production among project-based peace practitioners.

Data and Methods

Our analysis is based on 29 semi-structured, in depth, face to face interviews conducted between January 2019 and January 2023. The 2019 data collection was part of an assessment of Community Dialogue, a cross-community peacebuilding organization based in Belfast. Interviewees practiced community facilitation throughout Northern Ireland and across the border. Data from the 2019 interviews revealed the development of an integrated community of peacebuilding practitioners. Our 2022-2023 sample drew from a broad range of peacebuilding practitioners. Like Stanton’s research, our sample includes practitioners who linked their peacebuilding activity “directly to its intersection with their chosen profession as well as those for whom it was linked more indirectly” (Stanton, 2021, p. 7). For our study, we’ve defined “peacebuilding practitioners” as individuals engaged in constructive cross-community interactions at the grassroots level. The majority of our subjects were female and ranged from 33 to 79 years of age with 18 years of practice on average. They represented both sides of the deep historical divide: the Catholic Nationalist Republican and Protestant Unionist Loyalist communities.

The semi-structured interviews were based on a series of questions and prompts intended to explore the professional development of peace practitioners, the identification of best practices, and the future of peacebuilding in Northern Ireland. After transcribing the interviews, each researcher reviewed and coded all interviews. During debriefing sessions, we identified our emergent and unexpected findings. Although we were looking for common patterns, several outlier instances were also identified.

The interview data were supplemented by academic documentation and specific program reports to support participants’ recollections of community-based programs, their implementation, and outcomes. Participant observation of many local community events complemented the interview data.

Thematic Findings

We identified three themes from our interviews with peacebuilding practitioners: (1) a commitment to a chosen profession, (2) sources of inspiration, and (3) practice development. Our themes draw upon the guiding concepts in our literature review.

Throughout this section, practitioners when quoted are referred to by assigned pseudonyms.

Many identifying characteristics have been changed or are not revealed in our discussion.

Theme 1 - A “Chosen” Profession

In living “lives of commitment in a complex world,” (p. 4) to use a Parks Deloz et al. (1996) phrase, the word “chosen” can be understood as having a two-way meaning. Listening to the peace practitioners as they explained what they call “the work,” it seems the work somehow chose them as much as they made the decision themselves.

They did not expressly describe their work as a calling or a mission on behalf of the larger society. Yet this summarized understanding emerged from the stories the practitioners used to explain why and how they had careers encouraging Northern Ireland's people to engage together in responding constructively to their common problems. The practitioners' focus on Northern

Ireland's need for "a better, shared future" echoes the phrase "something larger" used by

Parks Deloz and his colleagues (1996) when summarizing their interviewees' motivation: They often refer to that 'something larger' as 'the work,' and whether manifest in action on behalf of better education, responsible business practices, participatory democracy, or environmental sustainability, at its core we heard a thrumming concern for a future in which life, 'the most basic bottom stuff,' could flourish (p. 197). As interviewers, we found the peace practitioners' common commitment compelling, particularly given their wide variety of backgrounds and the individual, unique, lived experiences they referenced to explain the sources of their perseverance in, as they often put it, "the work." All spoke in distinct and deeply personal ways. It seems a sense of need, hope, mission, or the work itself, undertaken in the wider Northern Ireland society, grounded their lives. As Kelleher (2017, p. 70) previously documented:

Practitioners see possibility, imagine past what others think is not possible. They name and link the issues to a potential future and explain the package to people. Such practitioners start with ideas about the future, then make it happen with practical projects as they become possible and brings others along. This is a rare way of working: the vision brings people in, and they create a body of work around it.

Variety also describes how the practitioners identified themselves in their work, including but not limited to community activist, community developer, community educator, women's activist, community organizer, social activist, dialog facilitator, and yes, peace practitioner. As Practitioner U explained, "people have really found a way to do something the only way that they knew how, to put their head above the parapet, to not sit back and say that's just the way things are here."

While the practitioners' origin stories differed, they commingled in reflecting what in Northern Ireland is understood as a common commitment to a "shared future." According to Parks Deloz et al. (1996), people arrive at a shared sense of ethical commitment and social responsibility through a three-phase developmental process, as identified in our literature review. The earliest phase, "connecting in community and with 'the other,'" focuses on the interviewees' formative experiences in explaining why they became peace practitioners. Practitioner comments generally reflected Northern Ireland's grassroots connections to family and place. For example, Practitioner E noted his family as "working class with socialist principles." Practitioner F elaborated with a reflection from her youth: I lived for nineteen years with no Catholic friends. Then my two best friends at university were Catholic. What was all that about really? One was from West Belfast. We met each other off the train and we were both shaking. And she grabbed my arm and said do you know where you're going? I said I have no idea. So, she said she would stay with me. We both were afraid. Now many of my good friends, my caring empathetic friends, are Catholics. . . . I want my children to be exposed to different experiences too so that they don't grow up with stereotypes, lies.

Practitioner N's explanation was deeply rooted in Derry/Londonderry Northern Ireland's history:

I never in my wildest dreams ever thought I would end up working as a practitioner in this field. Back then I worked in the shirt factories, and the shirt factories were, I suppose, like a community relations situation. (In Northern Ireland "community relations" refers to bridging the catholic/nationalist/republican and

protestant/unionist/loyalist divide.) It was in the shirt factories where there were women from everywhere. It was my first time interacting daily with someone who was different from me. We had many a conversation. I remember when the Omagh bomb happened, women were coming up to me and saying, ‘Look, it didn’t happen in our name. We’re so sorry.’

Some interviewees explained the origins of what became their career’s commitment as a reaction to negative experiences, some frightening. Practitioner K shared her story about her bus ride to school:

When I was thirteen years of age in 1974, . . . a man in a balaclava got on (the bus), put a gun to my head, and told the driver to get the kids off the bus. We were petrified. Then another guy came along and he said, ‘Get those kids back on the bus.’ Then he told the driver, ‘If tomorrow you come this way again you won’t have a bus.’ I can remember coming home crying. . . . I lived on a mixed street and was very naïve.

Practitioner P provides another example:

In 1969, the onset of the Troubles, we had to move out because our home was burned. . . . It was a terrifying experience for children and people, people all around you. . . . It didn’t happen to one side of the community. It happened to them all. (But) As a child it is sort of like an acculturation process. You are growing up with - they have done this and they have done that. So even coming into community relations work, anybody saying they don’t have a backpack with them isn’t being totally honest. It is how you open that backpack and unpack the things that are inside it and make your mind up as an adult. Dialogue would be a massive part of that unpacking. Practitioner M’s story, while also embedded in Northern Ireland’s painful history, took him deeper into the polarization’s violence:

In 1987 I was convicted to maximum prison for 34 years. I was a young man who grew up in an area where, you know, you had to be one of the boys. Word came in from the organization I was involved with to take command. There were a lot of things happening, protests that didn’t need to happen. Catholics walked on this side, Protestants on that side. You weren’t allowed to talk to each other. . . . I stopped that. It was too small a place. We needed to talk to each other because if we didn’t it was going to be a long time and it wouldn’t help any of us. Long story short, with other commanders, we agreed that prisoners could speak to each other.

Many of our interviewed practitioners acknowledged how their international experiences inspired or prepared them for their community work in Northern Ireland. It is commonplace for people in Northern Ireland to have family members and friends go overseas to live and work, or to have done so themselves, so we were not surprised when several of our respondents spoke of their formative learning about “the other” in another country.

Increasingly, people from other countries are relocating permanently to Northern Ireland. Through our interviews, the practitioners revealed how they think internationally, understanding themselves as functioning in an international context.

The following examples illustrate the range of international influences. One practitioner’s remembered cross-cultural situation was as the son of parents who had moved to Northern Ireland from a former British colony, and another had lived in Hong Kong and England for a few years. While at university, a practitioner had spent months doing research in Greece. Also, while employed at the University of Ulster’s INCORE, now the International Conflict Research Institute, another practitioner worked with people originally from Poland, the Philippines, India, and China.

Practitioner Y’s reflections presented another way of experiencing “the other:” I went to Khartoum when I was seventeen because my sister now lived there. I had met my brother-in-law maybe a year or two before. He picked me up from the airport. I said to him, ‘I didn’t realize there were so many shades of black.’ He said, “That’s really

interesting. I didn't know there were so many shades of pink.' So, he and I got along well. I was looking at the world in a different way. . . That these people were orange, and I was green. . . I didn't see it made a difference. Relevant comments from three interviewees cited Canada as a place to experience what could be termed constructive diversity. As Practitioner A explained:

[In Canada] we were outdoors all the time and with people from every walk of life all around us. Then straight through to Belfast at twelve years old to a secondary school with an intake 100% girls and 100 % Protestant. That was such a culture shock at twelve. It was something that I never ever could accept.

At the grassroots, projects having positive results over time and after outside support depends on local buy-in. People in the community must own it in all ways, from the initial idea and planning to management at all levels and given credit for the result. Practitioner W learned this significant lesson when his first career began in Nigeria on an international development project. The lesson has become a mainstay of his work ever since, including in Northern Ireland. He recalls:

My first instinct was to go in and get the well dug. It quickly became obvious that didn't work. Ownership, and therefore the business of engaging the community, the chief, various sectors, within the sectors, all that laborious conversational stuff both formal and informal, was critical to the long-term success of something being left at the end of all the hard work.

Theme 2 – Sources of Inspiration

Parks Daloz and his colleagues (1996) identify a second developmental phase experienced by people living lives of ethical commitment and social responsibility in a complex world. We have summarized this second phase as “constructing meaning and commitment, accepting contradictions.” All the Northern Ireland grassroots practitioner interviewees talked about both their personal experiences as well as the formal education, training, and/or written material that informed their professional practice. In other words, their sources of inspiration.

Parks Daloz et al. (1996) discuss their interviewees as developing critical, systemic thought, “the capacity to identify parts and the connections among them as coherent patterns, to see oneself as part of those patterns, and simultaneously to step outside and reflect evaluatively on them” (p. 113). As a significant element in the researchers' understanding of critical thinking, “perspective-taking” means that, “recognizing multiple frameworks as legitimate in their own terms invariably leads to contradictions” (p. 120). We found evidence of the same level of critical comparative thinking among the practitioners we interviewed.

In a divided society such as Northern Ireland, accepting contradictions must be built into the thinking of people deeply committed to creating a shared future. All the practitioners interviewed for this study reflected on how their careers had taken shape over time, and embedded in their meaningful life-defining experiences were reflections about how they came to their own understandings of the complexity and contradiction inherent in Northern Ireland's multiple perspectives. Noteworthy subthemes emerged from practitioner comments about their lived experiences.

International Careers

The first subtheme arose when a total of 19 practitioners included international experiences as contributing to the development of their practice. Six of these discussed their time spent living and working in places such as Liberia, Nigeria, Hong Kong, and Canada, and this number expands by seven more when Great Britain and Ireland are added.

In addition, four practitioners commented on their preparing and leading groups to international locations, such as World War I graveyards in Belgium where both unionists and nationalists are buried. Three more practitioners

cited their professional experiences abroad making presentations and engaging with peace practitioners in, for example, Israel, Palestine, Bosnia, and India.

Two additional interviewees noted how they wove international information into their practice. For example, according to Practitioner U:

You use theatre, art, music, and then very much learning from other areas of the world as well. One of the first projects I was involved in as a facilitator was the Right to Hope which was started in South Africa and became a global project. We worked with young people from both sides of the community in Northern Ireland, and both sides of the border. We took them on residential and introduced them to bands from South Africa, and we had Native American beadwork workshops, things like that. . . . We weren't totally insular. We did learn from outside as well.

Intellectual Inspiration

A second subtheme embedded in the practitioners' reflections was their mentioning specific intellectual influences, ideas provided by a wide range of published sources. For example, Freire's (1970) *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* was noted by three interviewees as a source of inspiration, and one practitioner added the related *Training for Transformation: A Handbook for Community Workers* written by Hope and Timmel (1984) reflecting their learning from work in Rhodesia/Zimbabwe. Two more interviewees cited ideas from Bohm's 2004 *On Dialogue*, another noted Lederach's general body of work as pivotal. Dan Bar-On at Ben Gurion University of the Negev provided several practitioners with significant inspiration, particularly during his visit to Northern Ireland. Another book providing pivotal insights was *Peace Comes Dropping Slow* by Lennon (2004).

Individual practitioners also noted more general sources of inspirational ideas. Two interviewees cited socialism as at the core of their commitment. Christianity was also mentioned, and particularly Quaker ideas as well as their practice was discussed by four interviewees. One specifically talked about the Quakers' overt support for peace projects via the Joseph Rowntree Charitable Trust in London which provided initial peace funding from the early 1970s.

The following comments made by Practitioner AA illustrate how interviewees often embedded pivotal ideas about the sources of their inspiration within the context of taking action. As doers, the practitioners often synthesized personal experience and training provided by idea generators such as Quakers. Practitioner AA recalls:

I remember a bomb going off one night. I live on the other side of the river, but the bomb actually rocked my house. The Quaker Peace Project had called a meeting for that night and I decided to go. . . . The Quakers said, "We are having a training session Tuesday, come along." . . . I thought "This isn't me, I don't really want to do this work," but I got caught up in the training and found it really interesting. . . . I ended up going back for four weeks and getting into the whole thing. I really loved the methodology. It was very innovative. . . . I worked with the Quaker groups for quite a long time, probably eight years or so.

Later in the interview this practitioner expressed her motivation as, "Why isn't anybody doing anything? That is the feeling that started me off."

Women's Issues

Women's issues surfaced as a third subtheme with six interviewees expressing them as either their core motivation or a central focus of their work. For example, Practitioner T asserted, "I am a human rights and equality and gender balance person. That's my passion. So, I work with women. I work with men too, but 99.9 percent of the work that I do is with women. It is about women's voices being heard." Practitioner P dedicated her practice

to support Belfast women in their own day-to-day lives. She was inspired by a community-based organization at the grassroots level, formed 35 years earlier during The Troubles.

Theme 3 – Practice Development

Our analysis elaborates on Stanton's (2021) theory of how "practical wisdom draws heavily on knowledge gained from the accumulation of experience" (p.122), identifying the value of CoPs in cultivating and expanding this wisdom. While engaging in a variety of occupations, all our interviewees have carried out a substantial number of specific projects requiring intercommunity interactions and collaboration. Two practitioners have careers in formal education. One is a writer, another a musician, and one more is a consultant in the field of social psychology. Two have worked for the University of Ulster's International Conflict Research Institute, INCORE, and two more for Glencree, the peace center in the Republic of Ireland. The majority spent their professional lives in voluntary sector organizations.

We discovered how this group of practitioners evolved into a highly cooperative and collaborative structure, reflecting many of the characteristics of a CoP. Local peace work "requires not only conflict and communication skills development but regular monitoring and coaching" (Reiman & Ropers, 2005, p. 38). Three subthemes provide a focus for explaining how the practitioners developed their own practice, their version of practical wisdom: learning in community, the value of context, and best practices.

Learning in Community

As Parks Daloz et al. (1996) explained, collaboration doesn't suggest a group think where everyone had to agree, rather, "there was a marked confidence in the value of bringing diverse groups of people together in a manner that made it possible for them to focus on common problems" (p. 205). Wenger (1998) and other CoP researchers (Pyrko et al., 2017) maintain that being a member of a CoP is not something that people are aware of; but, "they do still experience a sense of togetherness when, often owing to facing similar real-life problems, and not necessarily because of liking each other, they organize themselves around negotiating a practice that they all share and identify with" (Pyrko et al., 2017, p. 392). What makes a CoP successful over time is its ability to "generate enough interest, relevance, value added and tangible outcomes to attract and engage members" (Stephens et al., 2021, p. 223).

CoP researchers have documented how practice is developed in a variety of ways – seeking advice from others, sharing and reusing assets, discussing developments and identifying gaps (Wenger-Trayner et al., 2014; Pyrko et al., 2017; Hadjimichael & Tsoukas,

2019) – all of which were identified by our interviewees. As the Northern Ireland practitioners discussed their work, the development of their practice was a collaborative activity, learning with and from others.

Practitioners identified a specific community group or leader who facilitated their community relations training or their entry into the practitioner community. According to Practitioner W, the leaders of these groups "were very strong on the importance, not just being aware of each other's existence, but of the possibility of asking ourselves what we are at and why." From the start of their work, in the early 1970s and 80s for some of the practitioners, collaborative practice was the norm. More people became involved beginning in the late 1980s and during the 1990s, when the number of projects began expanding, and practitioners increased their sharing of learned experience. The value of these connections, as described by Practitioner H, included "having a place where we could go and have that honest conversation and say to people, 'I felt very unskilled, demotivated, and out of my depth. What are the solutions to that?'" This practitioner referred to her mentors as "a godsend."

Many identified Corrymeela, The Junction, the Community Relations Council, WAVE, Towards Understanding and Healing, Peace and Reconciliation Group, and Community Dialogue with providing regular access to specific workshops and facilitator trainings. These organizations were invaluable for skill development, but also for establishing interpersonal connections and networks. Practitioner O described the benefits of connecting with other practitioners:

Every time you engage, you meet a like-minded person, so there is an organic, unplanned, even unintended, process of establishing a network through practice. You make connections in the process of your work with people whom it seems clear are traveling the same path as yourself. Those connections evolve personally as friendships and mutual support mechanisms, and they also evolve as professional relationships. Why don't you come in and give that presentation to my group and why don't we try to target those people? And this person wouldn't talk to me, he wouldn't piss on me if I was on fire, could you have a chat with him?

Several interviewed practitioners characterized their practice development as

“learning by doing,” making a clear distinction from formal learning. This was the case for Practitioner N, who stated, “This is all on my own. This is not out of a book. It is one of the tools that I taught myself. Because you learn as you go along. You learn when you make mistakes.” Practitioner L echoed this: “Everything will feed into something. You learn something in one job that you bring into another one. You can't just see it as this is completely new. You have to use the skills that you have, to build on the skills you have.”

However, learning while doing was often characterized as a shared activity with more experienced practitioners, a reminder of how a key element of a CoP is the mutual engagement among members. Many of our interviewees worked together as Community Dialogue facilitators. They regularly engaged in mutual coaching and support as they prepared for their work and co-facilitated dialogues (Leon-Guerrero et al., 2019).

According to Practitioner U, “Having been in groups facilitated by really good facilitators really does help. You do need to observe how it's done well. You can pick stuff up, but you really need to experience it as well.” In fact, many practitioners prefer to co-facilitate because there is a practical value to co-facilitation. As Practitioner F explained, “I don't like to facilitate alone. I like to facilitate with me and somebody else because it gives you space to think. It gives you time to read people's faces. If you're facilitating and trying to do everything, you always miss something.” A facilitation was often described as an extemporaneous collaborative process with another practitioner. Practitioner X noted: It always helps enormously. The Towards Understanding and Healing model was co-facilitation. . . . There are to be drawbacks in that because you can depend on the other person and not take the initiative, but there also is . . . something could be happening, and I might be very involved in it, but . . . (the co-facilitator is) . . .

watching what's happening in the rest of the group and being able to say, so that we haven't lost touch with the group.

The Value of Context

The majority of our subjects earned university degrees, with two majoring in peace and conflict studies. As we've already noted, professional expertise was developed in other careers as educators, mediators, counselors, and administrators. Like Stanton (2021), we found evidence in our study of how context-knowledge was essential to the development of practical wisdom. In her research, Stanton (2021) documented five patterns of context:

place-space, framing, time-timing, fault lines, and relationships. She emphasized,

“Consideration of these nuanced dimensions of context tacitly and explicitly became a source of knowledge used to inform actions aimed at peacebuilding” (p.135).

For our subjects, place and space emerged as an important context in their practice development. According to Stanton (2021, p. 135), “each place and space influenced local identity construction, meaning-making, and cultural norms. . .” We discovered how place and space served as a personal marker, as a qualification to do this work and as a means to establish professional authority and credibility in the community. Practitioner T echoed what other interviewees described about the relationship between their individual place, space, and practice:

I am very fortunate probably because I am grassroots, because I am known. I know the issues. I live in the same communities that they live in. So, I know the issues and the stuff they have in common. . . . I find that if you are not on top of the issues within your community, you’re not working grassroots, and you don’t see . . . you don’t walk the walk or walk the talk within those communities - you can’t really sit there and empathize with people if you are not part of that. . . . Sometimes people sit and facilitate – I understand, I understand, I understand. Really the true understanding is walk in my shoes. I believe I walk those same streets. I cross over. I do not ask anybody to do anything that I am not prepared to do myself. That stands me in good faith.

Many practitioners were keenly aware of how their social place or positionality, whether defined by experience, age, politics, or some other social identity, shaped how they understood and engaged with community members and informed policy. Several spoke of how their positionality helped make meaning of their work. Practitioner K notes “Do you know what I think, most people in this line of work are in it for a reason. It is because something has happened in their own life.” Practitioner H corroborates:

Everything about my background, because we are products of where we come from, everything about my background as a practitioner is shaped by my experiences. If I haven’t had the experience, I cannot for one second understand why you have that viewpoint. But if you put me in a room with you and we have this conscious conversation, I can actually inquisitively ask . . . why you occupy that particular space or viewpoint.

Practitioner I observes:

You really had to have lived through the conflict to have the ability to have a conversation about it. There is a hierarchy of . . . your voice is less important because you didn’t lose anybody, or you didn’t actively participate, or you haven’t gone to jail, or whatever.

Stanton (2021) asserts that there is a connection between personal credibility and the personal trust that practitioners develop with residents, groups, or other stakeholders. Our interviewees did not explicitly make this connection, but 14 out of 29 identified trust, generally, as an important aspect of their practice. Other important aspects of practice are discussed in the next subtheme.

Best Practices

The practitioners exhibit a capacity to describe their practice in terms of specific methods and values they’ve developed individually and shared as a community. All were able to critically identify how specific strategies contribute to a good discussion and distinguish between their successes and challenges. Their vocabulary is consistent, reflecting a shared language and meaning with other practitioners. The stories tacitly demonstrated facilitators’ experience and expertise as well as their seriousness of purpose (Leon-Guerrero et al., 2019).

All the interviewees identified activities or strategies that were deemed central or valuable to their practice. More than half identified the importance of empathy as a pre-requisite to a successful conversation or as a desired result. As described by Practitioner A:

I think they learn empathy through the process. If the process is right, they can often, and they often express that they felt something different because they never had that feeling before. So, something has come. So, there can

be people who have empathy, just that personality. But definitely through that process empathy develops. An empathetic understanding, as I call it, develops. Walking a mile in somebody else's shoes develops.

Practitioners identified active listening and flexible, participant-led agendas as the most essential practices. Similar to the discussions about empathy, active listening was described as a pre-requisite and as an outcome.

Practitioner P explains:

They have to be prepared to listen. Sometimes people come in the room, and it is all about . . . I need to get this out. And that is what dialogue is about. It is spitting out the nuts and the bolts and then counting. . . . (But) if people can enter prepared to listen, they will get so much out of it because if you are not listening to me how do I know what you are saying? How can I understand what perspective you have, or where you are coming from, or, indeed, if I consider you have a valid point or not, or if I hear. . .

. Remember, the good Lord gave you two ears and one mouth. So. you kind of have to listen twice as hard as you talk.

When asked about the success of community facilitation, many did not identify a specific outcome; several defined the event itself as an outcome. In the case of community dialogues, Practitioner U stated, "We would say, 'the dialogue is the outcome.' The fact that you would have had people in the room together who have not been talking about the weather. They haven't been talking about the premiership football. They have been actually talking about the issues that affect their day to day lives in Northern Ireland." Practitioner F simply stated, "You can't do dialogue as a tick box exercise." Many practitioners described dialogue as a process and an opportunity. Practitioner W explained what a "corrective environment and space" is and how it can be produced:

We come in and we are very, very clear from the beginning that we bring no judgement to this situation. That we are going to invite people to hear different things, and these things from the other side of the house. And that we require everyone to sign up to an agreement that they will listen respectfully to what they hear on the understanding that they will get a chance to speak and be heard equally respectfully.

Practitioner Q offered this understanding:

That's what I mean about building the ground. The best way to build the ground is, of course, . . . you have to start it because they're looking to you to . . . but the best way is everybody brings a pocketful of soil and could say we built the ground together.

Not that the ground is built by the facilitator. We built it together.

Theme 4 - The Role of Northern Ireland's Peacebuilding Environment

We end our findings discussion with an emergent theme on how shifts in the larger institutional context affected the work of Northern Ireland's peace practitioners. Perhaps the most prominent, the 1998 Belfast (Good Friday) Agreement led to the United Kingdom government devolving specific powers to the Northern Ireland Assembly. Transferring decision-making on some aspects of budget allocations, including those funding peacebuilding projects, from Westminster to elected representatives in Northern Ireland made possible local participation in determining funding priorities, a shift from a predominantly top-down approach. However, our interviewed practitioners noted that challenges remained in striking the right balance between top-down decision-making and community involvement as in, for example, the setting of useful criteria and effective activities for local projects. Also problematic was the fact that high-profile community activists and gatekeepers, who had the ear of politicians, could influence the distribution of funding.

Another point raised during our practitioner interviews dealt with the top-down, relatively inflexible bureaucratic requirements that came to accompany the major increases in international funding. While expressing gratitude

for the substance and scale of the international contributions, some practitioners noted that they knew of effective grassroots people, with proven track records, who left project work in frustration because of the increasingly detailed directions and conditions required by funders.

Luna and Byrne (2021) also documented the distraction of the application process in their study of CSO leaders and funding agency development officers. According to the practitioners they interviewed, “the technocratic and bureaucratic nature of the EU Fund’s application processes and reporting procedures take peace workers away from their peacebuilding activities” (Luna & Byrne, 2021, p. 22). Byrne and his colleagues (2023) found the same - “many groups were constantly wrapped up in bureaucratic red tape as they attempted to access key peacebuilding monies” (p. 174).

In addition to dealing with discussions over the design of projects and their funding, local practitioners experienced the negative effects of Northern Ireland’s consociation governmental structure established by the 1998 Belfast Agreement. Knox (2010) explains,

“Thus far there has been a reluctance by the two main power-sharing parties (DUP and Sinn Fein) to prioritise social transformation, presumably because it could weaken the sectarian bases from which they draw their own political support” (p. 14). The Stormont government institutionalizes Northern Ireland’s deep historical division which gives political party leaders a vested interest in maintaining it.

The Northern Ireland Assembly and its devolved government remain prisoners of their own polarization and, as a consequence, governing institutions have not been functioning for at least forty percent of the time since 1999. Given the reality of local peace practitioners’ efforts to build bridges across the sectarian divide in the context of ongoing political sectarianism, Byrne et al.’s 2023 study found that “CSO leaders revealed deep schisms between the political sphere and the grassroots level” (p. 173). Yet local practitioners continued their work which sometimes was, as one of the study’s interviewees put it, “an uphill fight often achieving takeoff regardless of the politicians. We carried on despite the difficulties” (Byrne et al., 2023, p. 173).

Doran (2010) observes how civil society in Northern Ireland perseveres in its facilitation of constructive, potentially transformative intercommunity interactions: They conform with the processes, structures and ethics associated with relatively stable, democratic non-governmental organisations who – in the pursuit of a liberal peace – steer a path between addressing sectarianism and prejudice and avoidance of any perception that they are attempting to delegitimize the dominant cultural and political projects espoused by the political leaderships of British Unionism-Loyalism and Irish Nationalism-Republicanism. . . . Most community relations activity operates within and through the community and voluntary sector networks (p. 16, 18). In support of Doran’s assertion, our research affirmed the effectiveness of the practitioners’ focus on local participation in activities featuring direct engagement with the other. They have been able to persist over decades because of their shared community of practice and clearheaded focus on the feasibility, indeed the necessity of a shared future. Practitioner CC offered a comment related to the inability of Northern Ireland’s political establishment to break free from ongoing sociopolitical polarization. Unprompted, she hopefully observed, “absent leadership within the political institutions, there is a bit more space for leadership from elsewhere.”

The Work Continues

Persevering during the several interruptions in Stormont’s representative institutions, Brexit’s future impacts, and the ongoing constitutional issue, Northern Ireland’s community/voluntary sector engages local people to work together on common problems.

Their practice remains relevant because it illustrates what MacGinty (2013) refers to as a “bottom-up process.” As MacGinty (2013) explains, they continue to facilitate:

conversations for community members to realise that they have more in common with ‘the other’ community than they realized . . . In this sense, (the process) refers to the ability of individuals and communities to learn about themselves (including hard lessons) and about other communities (p. 30).

MacGinty et al. (2007) also emphasizes the importance of the “soft processes,” the “affective and emotional dimensions, often overlooked by approaches that favor institution building, that are central to the success of peacebuilding” (p. 9). Lennon’s (2004) explanation of the work offers more elaboration which, in its essence, distills down to experiencing complexity, and building relationships, in an open-ended process with ground rules. Several of the practitioners interviewed for this study explained how individual and community learning happens, and in so doing they illustrated MacGinty’s and Lennon’s understanding of the process. As they put it, facilitated cross-community conversation helps participants to “see people as human beings first and foremost,” because they are “encouraged to think differently,” are “OK with being confused,” and engage in the process of “building the ground” with the goal of “caring and daring” to “bring about change.”

Often an elusive concept, effectiveness can be defined as the ability to carry on over an extended timeframe by remaining relevant, valid, and in demand amid changing circumstances. Clearly, this is the case for Northern Ireland’s grassroots peace practitioner community as they have persisted in their work over the decades of The Troubles’ and into the present. Their commendable track record continues as they recognize local needs and initiate new projects at the interfaces of a society that retains its deep divisions.

Practitioners described their most recent projects as not overtly focusing on crosscommunity interactions yet continuing to reveal stories of the other. This element was embedded in the design of particular projects, for example, Practitioner J’s description of the Human Library.

An effective method for the human books to tell their stories is to put the people attending into groups of three or four. Each group hears from one of the human books, and then moves on to the next one. There is a whole network now of people who were the books, and they support each other. They understand the impact of telling their story as raising awareness. They can see the change in people’s attitudes. Each “human book” has a title indicating the essence of the story, such as domestic abuse survivor, or living with blindness. The human books share their life experiences in various formats, often in schools. The storytellers include people with a Troubles legacy such as an ex-combatant or a former police officer or soldier.

Another example of a project’s having intercommunity activities built in was for the Causeway Coast and Glens Borough Council. As explained by Practitioner R, the grant funding for capital building projects was to improve community centers. At the same time the funder required engaging in intercommunity planning and operation. So cross community training was needed for those in the Council responsible for remodeling and operating the centers. Practitioner R observes:

You would have members of the Gaelic Athletic Association sitting beside the Royal British Legion. So, there would be a lot of trepidation sitting alongside people that you don’t ever meet or come across. . . . We really worked hard to do those workshops, and we got them to focus on what was important to them, to see the bigger picture of what they were doing for their community. . . . Taking them through that journey was one of the most rewarding things. . . . To hear the people from the two communities say, ‘We share the same problems. The next training, you come with us, and we can get the cost down.’ . . . Number one for us was making sure our dialogue

sessions were interesting enough that they'd want to come back. . . . And they got to the point where they all came together and developed a strategy to put to the politicians and counselors.

Practitioner R's comment illustrates the viability of a conclusion made by Knox and McCrory (2018) about the potential of Northern Ireland's community councils to, "lead the way and demonstrate that well-being or an improvement in the quality of life of its citizens is what matters. In so doing, it will tackle limitations of pre-existing approaches" (p. 24).

Practitioner BB's explanation of his current project provides another example in which the ostensible objectives do not include building bridges across the deep historical divide, yet this is inherent given the Northern Ireland's lived reality. Foyle River Gardens, currently in its initial design and search for funding phase, assumes a shared future for people living along the Foyle River, in Northern Ireland counties as well as those in the Republic of Ireland. As Participant BB explained, the project is to be a model of good practice in the era of climate change, and will include a nursery growing broadleaf trees, particularly oaks. These have been native to the island of Ireland since time immemorial. Even the name of

Practitioner BB's hometown, on the Foyle River in Derry/Londonderry, is derived from Doire, a Gaelic word meaning oak grove. He said the project will, "Take trees from here to every place on the island of Ireland that has Derry in its name, there are about 1,600 of them." Clearly, the shared challenges peace practitioners take on continue to be substantial. **Conclusion**

As we have documented, the practitioners' dedicated persistence benefits from their well-developed practical wisdom, as they continue engaging in their community of practice, designed to advance the workable common good of living peacefully together. We have provided space for practitioners to speak for themselves in revealing sources of their inspiration and commitment to a common good, as signaled by the Parks Dalos et al. (1996) analysis. Our interviewees' comments also highlighted the applicability of Stanton's (2021)

"practical wisdom" concept, as it can be merged with Wenger's (2002) community of practice (CoP) in providing a layered understanding of the practitioners at work. Most of our interviewees have been doing the work over decades, some since the 1980s and even earlier. They have experience in a wide variety of projects over the course of their careers. Many of the practitioners have not formally applied dialogue's praxes as such, but all have incorporated intercommunity interactions as part of their projects.

The interviewed practitioners employ their own hybrid professional practice having elements of relevant formal education and organizationally sanctioned training, and yet learned and developed in a highly collaborative, interactive, lateral learning process with others who also have engaged in similar grassroots work. Learning by doing and interacting with others comes naturally to grassroots practitioners. They recognize the benefits to be derived from group work with local people because their own experiences are locally based. Embedded in their own communities, the practitioners have very different personalities and represent a wide variety of demographic and social backgrounds. While the practitioners understand that connecting with others as individuals is the point, the cooperative practice they have developed as a CoP fits naturally into grassroots community settings. As a semi-formalized way of working, it lacks hierarchy in its openness and mutual respect and has proven effective over the decades.

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